

BUKHARA KHANATE DURING SUBHANKULIKHAB PERIOD

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Annotation: The article reveals the nature of the scientific and creative activity of the Ashtarkhani ruler of the Bukhara Khanate, Subkhanqulikhan. Subkhanqulikhan's reforms in the field of medicine, and his relations with the governors of the time, are detailed in the article.

Keywords: Subkhanqulikhan, Ashtarkhani, Turdi Ferghani, medicine, Subkhani medicine, Do rush-shifo, Nishani, Lub-lavoih.

Khan of Bukhara from Ashtarkhani. Governor of Balkh in 1651-80. After Nadrmuhammad Khan became the Khan of Bukhara, he appointed his son Subhanqulikhan as the governor of the city of Soli Sarai, and then of the Balkh region (1642). Soon after, he was removed from this position and became the governor of Kakhmerd. After Subhanquli Khan's brother Abdulaziz Khan removed his father from power and became the khan of Bukhara, Subhanquli Khan went to Balkh - to his father. Subhanqulikhan firmly established himself in the Balkh region and in 1651 won the governorship of Balkh and Badakhshan. Subhanqulikhan pursued independent politics from Bukhara. In 1658, peace was reached between Bukhara and Balkh through the mediation of Abdul Ghaffar Khoja, the elder of Abdulaziz Khan, and Subhankuli Khan officially recognized the authority of his brother. According to Muhammad Yusuf Munshii, on February 2, 1680, the aged Abdulaziz Khan handed over the throne of Bukhara Khanate to Subhanqulikhan and left for Hajj. In order to strengthen the central government, Subhankuli Khan increased the amount of taxes and increased his army. When Anusha Khan's successor, Arang Muhammad Khan, invaded

Bukhara in 1687, Subhanquli Khan did not limit himself to repulsing this attack, instead of the khan who was killed in 1688, he installed his deputy, Amir Niyaz, the doorkeeper (Shahniyaz) on the throne of Khiva. In this way, the Khanate of Khiva was again annexed to Bukhara, as in the time of Abdullah Khan II, and the only Uzbek state was established in the region. Diplomatic relations of the Bukhara khanate with Eastern countries improved during the reign of Subhankuli Khan. In 1689, Aurangzeb from the Baburis, Zabardast Khan, and Ottoman Turkish Sultan Ahmed II in 1691 sent ambassadors led by Mustafa Chavush to Bukhara. Between 1671 and 1687, letters were exchanged several times between Subhonqulikhan and Aurangzeb.

He wrote treatises on scientific astrology called "Ihya at-tibbi Subhaniy" ("Treatment according to Subhaniy's medicine"), "Lubb ul-lavoih ul-qamar fil-ikhtiyarot" ("The essence of the moon addresses in determining the lucky hour"). Subhankulikhan wrote poems under the pseudonym "Nishani" and recited poems at concerts held in the palace. Subhonquli Khan was buried in Dakhmai Shahan (near the tomb of Abdullah Khan II) in the Bahauddin complex near Bukhara. Many architectural monuments were built by Subhonqulikhan in Balkh and Bukhara, including a madrasa in Balkh, Dor ush-shifa in Bukhara, a large pond in Registan; A salam khana and a mosque were built in Ark, as well as a church in Aminabad. In this period, medical science and literature developed especially. In addition to treating patients, scientific works were also carried out in the hospital. Subhonquli Khan had a rare library of medical books. He wrote treatises on science and astrology called "Ihya at-tibbi Subhani" ("Treatment according to Subhani's medicine"), "Lubb ul-lawayih ul-qamar fil ikhtiyorot" ("The essence of the moon addresses in determining the lucky hour"). A copy of the manuscript of his work "Ihyo at-tibbi Subhani" is kept in the library in Budapest. Subhonqulikhan wrote poems under the pseudonym "Nishani" and he also recited poems at the concerts held in the palace. "Dor ush-shifo" madrasa hospital was

built in 1697. It has 18 rooms. In front of the hospital, auxiliary buildings such as a pharmacy, a clinic, and a library have also been built. In addition to providing services to patients, cultural events were also held in this place. Subhonqulikhan ruled Bukhara Khanate for more than 20 years. He died in 1702 at the age of 77. Subhonquli Khan was buried in Dakhmai Shahon (near the tomb of Abdullah Khan II) in the Bahauddin Naqshband complex near Bukhara. Before his death, he appointed his grandson Muhammad Muqim Khan as the heir to the throne. At this time Muqim Khan was in Balkh and the prince of Bukhara, Ubaidullah Khan, who relied on the support of the palace officials and the army, ascended the throne. Muqim Khan sends his ambassadors to Ubaidullah Khan. Cold relations between the two countries lasted for five years. Muqim Khan turned Balkh into a separate province from Khanate with the help of his father Mahmudbi's repression. As a result of the conspiracy of 1707, Muqim Khan was killed, and the struggle for the throne stopped. By the time of Subkhanquli Khan, great changes took place in the development of science. Subkhanqulikhan knew the science of medicine, he also created works related to the science of medicine. In particular, he has two works on medicine. His first work was written in Turkish (Uzbek language) and called "Tibbi Subkhaniy". This work provides detailed information about methods of diagnosis and treatment of various diseases. This work of Subkhanquli Khan was so important that even this work served as a major guide for judges of that time. His second work consists of 8 parts called "Subkhan's life-giving medicine". This work is also considered one of the important works in the field of medicine. In particular, issues related to the quality preparation and use of drugs are covered in each of its parts. Plants that are beneficial for human health are also mentioned in the work. Both of these works are considered to be perfectly written works of their time. The reason is that these works are inextricably linked. Subhonqulikhan ruled Bukhara Khanate for more than 20 years. He died in 1702 at the age of 77. Subhonquli Khan was buried in Dakhmai Shahon (near the tomb

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Summary. In short, many diplomatic relations were conducted with the Ottomans during the Ashtarkhanid period. In particular, rulers such as Abdul Baqi Muhammad Khan, Nadir Muhammad Khan, Abdulaziz Khan, Subhan Quli Khan, Ubaidullah Khan, and Abul Fay Khan corresponded with the Ottoman sultans, strengthened the relations between the two countries and raised them to a higher level.

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